

BARICITINIB IN PLASMA USING A MINIMAL 50 μ L SAMPLE

VOLUME: ADVANCED LC-MS/MS METHODOLOGY.

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory condition affecting 0.5–1% of adults, characterized by joint pain, swelling, and fatigue. Baricitinib, a Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitor, is effective in treating moderate to severe RA, particularly in patients unresponsive to tumor necrosis factor inhibitors. This study aimed to develop a rapid, sensitive, and robust LC-MS/MS method for quantifying baricitinib in human plasma. The method utilizes a simple protein precipitation extraction technique, requiring only 50 μ L of plasma. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a C18 column and a mobile phase of 0.1% formic acid in methanol. The assay demonstrated excellent selectivity, precision, and accuracy over a range of 0.1–1000 ng/mL. Recovery rates for baricitinib and the internal standard tolbutamide were 97.65% and 91.04%, respectively. Stability tests confirmed baricitinib's stability under various conditions, including freeze-thaw cycles and prolonged storage. This validated method provides a reliable tool for baricitinib quantification in clinical settings, facilitating therapeutic drug monitoring and pharmacokinetic studies to optimize RA treatment.

Keywords: *Rheumatoid arthritis, Baricitinib, LC-MS/MS, Janus kinase inhibitor, Therapeutic drug monitoring.*

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a progressive, chronic autoimmune disorder predominantly affecting the joints. It manifests as a systemic inflammatory condition, impacting 0.5–1% of the adult population. RA is characterized by persistent synovial joint inflammation, leading to symmetrical inflammatory polyarthritis and progressive erosive destruction of joints, including cartilage and bone deformity and damage [1]. Major symptoms include joint pain, inflammation, swelling, stiffness, and generalized fatigue, with alternating episodes of flares and remissions. RA can also significantly affect other organs such as the eyes, heart, and lungs [2-5].

Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors are anti-rheumatic drugs targeting intracellular kinase. JAKs are crucial for the signalling of many cytokines and hematopoietic growth and development [6]. Baricitinib (Figure 1), a selective and reversible JAK1 and JAK2 inhibitor, is widely used to treat moderate to severe active RA in adult patients who have had an inadequate response to one or more tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (TNFis) [7-8]. Baricitinib has shown dose-dependent efficacy for up to 24 weeks, significantly improving the signs and symptoms of RA in patients [9]. Patients treated with baricitinib have reported consistent pain relief regardless of the degree of inflammation control. Additionally, baricitinib treatment improves RA disease control, provides rapid pain relief, enhances work productivity, and is cost-effective compared to other RA medications [10]. Patients with hereditary immunodeficiency syndrome have shown a complete disappearance of rheumatoid nodules following 12 months of baricitinib treatment, and the drug has also significantly improved the signs and symptoms of systemic lupus erythematosus [11].

Baricitinib is rapidly absorbed after oral administration, reaching peak plasma concentrations in approximately one hour. Its oral bioavailability is 79%, and it is moderately bound (about 50%) to plasma proteins, primarily albumin [12]. Baricitinib is primarily metabolized by the CYP3A4 enzyme and is a substrate of P-glycoprotein (Pgp), organic anion transporter (OAT) 3, multidrug and toxic extrusion protein (MATE) 2-K, and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP). The pharmacokinetics of baricitinib are influenced by food and concurrent administration of other drugs. The therapeutic effects and safety of baricitinib are related to the rate and extent of absorption [7]. Probenecid, for example, increases the extent of baricitinib absorption, doubling the AUC_{0-inf} and reducing renal clearance to 69%, without significantly increasing the rate of absorption (C_{max}) [13]. Conversely, rifampicin, a potent CYP3A inducer, decreases baricitinib AUC without affecting C_{max} [14]. No clinically significant drug interactions have been reported between baricitinib and CYP substrates, inhibitors, and inducers. Ketoconazole (a CYP3A inhibitor) and fluconazole (a CYP2C19/CYP2C9/CYP3A inhibitor) do not significantly affect baricitinib pharmacokinetics, although an OAT3 inhibitor reduces baricitinib clearance. A high-fat meal does not affect baricitinib AUC but reduces C_{max} by approximately 29%, with a 3-hour delay in t_{max}, without clinical impact [15].

Baricitinib's safety profile is debated. Some studies indicate that it is a safe and well-tolerated over 24 weeks in patients with moderate to severe RA [9, 16, 17]. However, other studies suggest that it induces a stable dose-response increase in LDL-C and HDL-C levels, elevates the risk of thrombosis [18], and increases the risk of infections, particularly herpes zoster and gastrointestinal perforations [19-20]. Although human data on baricitinib's embryotoxicity and teratogenicity are limited, preclinical animal studies have shown its potential for these effects and adverse impacts on bone development in utero at higher dosages [21].

RA therapy often includes a combination of antirheumatic drugs, JAK inhibitors, biologics (such as TNF- α or IL-6 inhibitors), and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Thus, it is important to study baricitinib pharmacokinetics in various therapeutic contexts. Currently, TKIs including baricitinib are administered as a fixed dosage without considering inter-individual differences. While this approach may be practical, optimal therapeutic plasma concentration can be achieved through dosage individualization using therapeutic drug monitoring, ensuring rapid and effective clinical response with minimal adverse effects [22].

Validated analytical methods for measuring baricitinib in biological fluids are scarce. Existing methods either measure baricitinib in combination with other drugs using low-purification techniques like protein precipitation with low sensitivity and long run time [23], or employ solid phase extraction, which is costly and requires large sample volumes [24]. Thus, developing a fast, sensitive method for analyzing baricitinib in biological fluids is crucial for better understanding its performance in therapeutic drug monitoring and clinical trials. This study aims to develop and validate a novel, simple, sensitive, selective, rapid, rugged, and reproducible LC-MS/MS method for the quantitative determination of baricitinib in human plasma using a small sample volume. The method described herein offers high sensitivity, selectivity, and rapid analysis, utilizing only 50 μ L of human plasma through simple protein precipitation extraction.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Baricitinib and Tolbutamide Obtained from TLC Pharmachem, USP. All other chemicals and solvents were purchased from S.D fine chemicals Mumbai. The control human plasma sample was procured from Doctors Pathological Labs (Hyderabad, India). Chemical structures are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Chemical Structures of A) Baricitinib B) Tolbutamide

Instrumentation

A triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (API 4000, Toronto, Canada) was linked to a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system (1200 Series Agilent Technologies, Germany). The programme Analyst 1.4.1 (SCIEX) was used to process the data. The electro-spray ionization process was carried out using the positive mode and a Unit Resolution.

Detection

By optimising the mass parameters, the precursor ions of Baricitinib $[M+H]^+$ (m/z : 372.2) and Tolbutamide $[M+H]^+$ (m/z : 271.1) were converted into the product ions of m/z : 251.1, m/z : 91.1, using a source temperature of 500 °C and an ion spray voltage of 5500 volts. All gas channels with nitrogen: heater gas, nebulizer gas (35 psi each), curtain gas (20 psi) and CAD gas (5 psi). Without a split, the source flow rate is 500 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

The following potentials are measured: 10 V for the entrance, 65 V for the analyte, and 75 V for the internal standard; 35 V for the collision energy of the analyte and the internal standard; and 14 V for the analyte and 16 V for the internal standard at the collision cell exit. Both the parent and product ions' mass spectra were shown in Figures 2.0–3.0.

Figure II. Mass spectra (Q1 and Q3) of Baricitinib

Figure III. Mass spectra (Q1 and Q3) of Tolbutamide

Chromatographic conditions

At a temperature of 40°C, chromatographic separation was carried out using a 50 $\times$ 4.6 mm, 2.7 μm column manufactured by Ascentis Express. At a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min, the mobile phase was utilised, which consisted of 0.1% formic acid in methanol (40:60 v/v). For the purposes of chromatography and extractability, tolbutamide was used as an internal standard. The internal standard and drug were separated with average retention duration of 0.78 ± 0.2 min and 0.83 ± 0.2 min, respectively, over a 2-minute run.

Preparation of Standards and Quality Control (QC) Samples

Baricitinib and Tolbutamide were dissolved in methanol to create stock solutions with concentrations of 50.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ each. The internal standard spiking solution, with a concentration of 20.0 ng/mL, was produced by diluting the Tolbutamide standard stock solution in 50% methanol. The stock solutions and internal standard spiking solutions were held under refrigeration (2–8

°C) until analysis. The Baricitinib stock solution, which is the standard solution, was combined with drug-free plasma that was being tested. This resulted in concentration levels of 0.100, 0.500, 1.00, 10.00, 20.00, 40.00, 80.00, 100.00, 500.00, and 1000.00 ng/mL for the analytical standards. For the quality control standards, the concentration levels were 0.3, 600, and 900 ng/mL. These solutions were then stored in a freezer at a temperature of -30°C until they were analyzed. The appropriate aqueous standards were produced using a reconstitution solution consisting of Methanol and 0.1% Formic acid in a ratio of 40:60. These standards were then stored under refrigeration at temperatures between 2-8 °C until they were ready for analysis.

Sample preparation

By utilizing liquid-liquid extraction, the medicine and internal standard (IS) were extracted from plasma samples. In order to reach this goal, 50µL of an internal standard (20.0 ng/mL) and 50µL of a plasma sample (with the matching concentration) were mixed in labeled polypropylene tubes and quickly shaken using a vortex shaker. A 0.5N sodium carbonate solution and 2.5 mL of methyl tertiary butyl ether, the extraction solvent, were added and stirred vigorously for 10 minutes afterward. A further step involved centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes at 20°C for the samples. Following that, the liquid components of each sample were transferred to their respective polypropylene vials. After that, we put each sample in a nitrogen tank and kept it at 40 degrees Celsius so it might evaporate. The dried residue was revived by swiftly agitating it with a vortex after adding 500 µL of reconstitution solution. The last step was to bring the sample into the LC-MS/MS system by transferring it into auto-sampler vials.

Selectivity and specificity

Six separate blank plasma samples were used to evaluate the selectivity of the procedure. Prior to co-elution, these samples underwent pretreatment and analysis to determine whether any endogenous compounds could potentially interfere with the analyte and internal standard. Chromatographic peak identification was made possible by differentiating the analyte and internal standard (IS) based on their retention durations and MRM responses. As a general rule, the average peak area of Baricitinib's Limit of Quantification (LOQ) must be more than 20% of the peak area of Baricitinib in blank samples at the comparable retention time. Blank samples should also not show a peak area for Tolbutamide that is more than 5% of the average peak area of the LOQ for Tolbutamide for the same retention period. Figure IV.0 to V.0 displayed the chromatograms and showed the plasma blank and lower limit QC.

Figure IV -Blank plasma chromatogram of interference-free Baricitinib and Tolbutamide

Figure V. Chromatogram of LOQ sample (Baricitinib and Tolbutamide)

Recovery

The determination of the extraction recovery of Baricitinib and Tolbutamide from plasma was conducted by the analysis of quality control samples. The recovery at three different concentrations (0.3, 600.0, and 900.0 ng/mL) was calculated by comparing the peak areas obtained from the plasma sample with those obtained from the standard solution that was mixed with the residual of blank plasma. An 85% or higher recovery rate was deemed sufficient to achieve the desired level of recovery.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ)

The limit of detection (LOD) is a measure that represents the minimum concentration in a sample that can be distinguished from background noise, but cannot be accurately measured. The limit of detection (LOD) was established by comparing the test findings of samples containing known quantities of analytes with blank samples, using s/n ratio of 3:1.

The limit of quantification (LOQ) refers to the minimum concentration of an analyte that can be accurately and precisely quantified. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was determined through the analysis of a series of mobile phase and plasma standards containing a known quantity of Baricitinib.

Matrix effect

In order to anticipate the fluctuation of matrix effects in samples obtained from different plasma batches, the matrix effect was assessed by measuring the matrix factor, which was computed using the following formula.:

$$\text{Matrix Factor} = \frac{\text{Peak response ratio in presence of extracted matrix (post-extracted)}}{\text{Peak response ratio in aqueous standards}}$$

Peak response ratio in aqueous standards

Six samples were obtained from the blank biological matrices, which were extracted in triplicate. The samples were subsequently post-spiked with a water-based standard at the QC level midpoint. We compared the post-spiked samples to water-based standards with the same concentration. The overall precision of the matrix factor is measured by the coefficient of variation (CV), which should be less than 15%.

Calibration curve, Precision and Accuracy

Baricitinib concentrations in human plasma were measured over a wide range, from 0.1 to 1000.0 ng/mL, to create the calibration curve. The quadratic model and weighted $1/x^2$ regression analysis were used to create the calibration curve. The ratio of Baricitinib peak area to Tolbutamide, in ng/mL, was plotted against the ratio of Baricitinib concentration, to create a graph. For this investigation, we made five copies of both the standard samples and the qc samples used to create the calibration curve. The accuracy and precision of the calibration points' back-calculated concentrations should not exceed 15% of their nominal values, and should preferably fall within a range of 15%. Nevertheless, for the LLOQ to be satisfied, the accuracy and precision ought to be within $\pm 20\%$ and $<20\%$, respectively. Tables 1.0 to 2.0 display the results.

TABLE I- Calibration curve details

Spiked Plasma Conc (ng/mL)	Concentration measured	CV (%) n = 5	Accuracy %
0.100	0.103	2.17	103.00
0.500	0.5012	0.50	100.24
1.000	1.032	2.77	103.20
10.000	10.038	0.27	100.38
20.000	20.02	0.06	100.10
40.000	40.2192	0.84	100.55
80.000	80.045	0.03	100.06
100.000	100.05268	0.01	100.05
500.000	501.86876	0.80	100.37
1000.000	1001.432	0.31	100.14

TABLE II- Precision and accuracy results

Spiked Plasma Conc (ng/mL)	Within-run			Between-run		
	Concentration Measured (n=6) (ng/mL)	% CV	% Accuracy	Concentration Measured (n=30) (ng/mL)	% CV	% Accuracy
0.300	0.30	3.67	100.44	0.29	3.24	97.34
600.00	584.87	1.56	97.48	589.87	1.29	98.31
900.00	898.67	0.56	99.85	887.89	1.53	98.65

Stability (Freeze-thaw, Autosampler, Benchtop, Long-term) of Baricitinib in Plasma

After three freeze-thaw cycles, six samples were extracted from a deep freezer; these samples included both low- and high-quality controls, as per the clinical procedure. Each of the three cycles—24, 36, and 48 hours—involved keeping the samples at -20°C . Additionally, after 45 days of storage at -30°C , the investigation was performed to determine the long-term stability of Baricitinib in the quality control samples. With control concentrations, we examined the autosampler's stability following 54.5

hours of storage in the autosampler tray. Using regulated concentrations, the benchtop's stability was tested over a 25-hour period. The stability samples and the calibration curve standards that were added recently were both processed and extracted at the same time. The stability samples should show a level of accuracy within $\pm 15\%$ of their nominal concentrations and a precision of no more than 15%. The results were laid down in a table. 3.0.

TABLE III- Stability studies details

Spiked Plasma Conc (ng/mL)	Room temperature stability		Autosampler stability		Long term stability		Freeze and Thaw stability	
	25 Hr		54.5 hr		45 days		Cycle 3 (48 hr)	
	Concn measured (n=6) (ng/mL) (mean)	CV (n=6) (%)	Concn measured (n=6) (ng/mL) (mean)	CV (n=6) (%)	Concn measured (n=6) (ng/mL) (mean)	CV (n=6) (%)	Concn measured (n=6) (ng/mL) (mean)	CV (n=6) (%)
0.300	0.300	0.623	0.300	0.830	0.300	2.13	0.300	2.09
900.00	904.036	0.176	910.800	0.400	905.000	0.78	904.036	0.40

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method development and validation

Its selectivity, sensitivity, and repeatability make LC-MS/MS a popular clinical pharmacokinetics analytical method. This project aims to develop and validate an easy, highly responsive, rapid, robust, and consistent assay method for correctly quantifying Baricitinib in human plasma samples. Multiple trials optimised the chromatographic conditions, including mobile phase composition and nature, column selection, and extraction methods like solid phase, precipitation, and liquid-liquid extraction, to improve Baricitinib and Tolbutamide signal. MS optimisation was done by immediately infusing Baricitinib and Tolbutamide solutions into the mass spectrometer's ESI source. The needle voltage, capillary voltage, source temperature, nebulizer gas, heater gas, and desolvation gases are important ESI source parameters. These parameters were adjusted to optimise spray form and ionise protonated ionic Baricitinib and Tolbutamide molecules. The product ion spectra of Baricitinib exhibited a high concentration of fragment ions with a mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of 271.1. The product ion spectra of Tolbutamide showed a large concentration of fragment ions at 91.1 m/z. To accomplish a fast and specific LC approach, mass spectrometer parameters were adjusted and chromatographic conditions, including mobile phase, column, and extraction process, were optimised. A mobile phase of 0.1% formic acid in methanol (40:60 v/v) separated and eluted well. The flow rate was 0.5 mL/min and the injection volume was 5 μ L. Chromatography was optimised using a liquid-liquid extraction approach and a 50 $\times$ 4.6 mm, 2.7 μ m Ascentis Express C18 column.

Selectivity and Specificity

The evaluation of Baricitinib and Tolbutamide by MRM functions exhibited high selectivity, without the presence of any interfering substances. The chromatograms acquired from plasma samples containing Baricitinib at a concentration of 0.1 ng/mL and Tolbutamide at a concentration of 20.0 ng/mL.

LOD & LOQ

Even while dealing with low quantities of Baricitinib, the instrument's detection capabilities were determined using the limit of detection. An estimated limit of detection of 2.5 fg was achieved after injecting 5 μ l of a solution with a concentration of 0.5 pg/mL. There was a signal-to-noise ratio of 3-5 or higher. We found that the minimum concentration on the calibration curve, which was set at 0.5 ng/mL, was the limit of quantification for this approach.

Matrix effect

Extraction was performed three times on each of six sets of blank biological matrices. The aqueous standard was subsequently combined with these sets at both the Low and High QC levels. By switching up the injections, we were able to compare the mixtures to neat standards of the same concentration. For LQC, the matrix factor %CV is 6.37, while for MQC, it is 3.66. At their respective retention durations, the analyte and internal standard (IS) did not cause any ions to be suppressed or enhanced.

Calibration curve standards, Precision and Accuracy

The calibration curves were generated by plotting the peak area ratio (Baricitinib/Tolbutamide) against the concentration of Baricitinib. The calibration exhibited linearity across the concentration range of 0.1 - 1000.0 ng/mL. The coefficient of variation (CV%) was below 5% and the Accuracy varied between 100.05% and 103.20%. All curves (Table 1) exhibited determination coefficients (r^2) over 0.9960. Table 2 demonstrates that the coefficient of variation within batches was below 15%, and the accuracy varied between 97.5% and 102.5%. The coefficient of variation (CV%) between batches was below 15%, indicating low variability. The Accuracy values ranged from 97.3% to 99.0%, demonstrating high precision. These results demonstrate the satisfactory dependability and consistency of this procedure within the specified range of analysis.

Stability (Freeze-thaw, Autosampler, Benchtop, Long term)

The stability of the analyte, Baricitinib, in plasma was assessed by subjecting it to three freeze-thaw cycles (-30°C to room temperature). The concentrations varied between 93 and 112.0% of the theoretical levels. The Baricitinib did not experience any

noticeable deterioration even after being stored in the autosampler tray for 54.5 hours. The final concentrations of Baricitinib were found to be between 94.0% and 112.0% of the expected values, indicating a high level of accuracy. There was no noticeable decrease in the quality of Baricitinib even after being stored at room temperature for 25 hours. Final Baricitinib concentration accuracy was 101.40% to 100.45% of predicted values. After 45 days at -20°C, quality control samples were tested for Baricitinib stability. Concentration accuracy was 97.48%–101.30 percent of theoretical values. The results confirmed Baricitinib's stability in human plasma after 45 days at -20°C.

Recovery

After preparing the samples with Liquid-liquid extraction with Methyl tertiary butyl ether, the recovery was assessed at control levels of Baricitinib by comparing the plasma samples' peak areas with the solvent samples' peak areas. Three different concentrations of Baricitinib were tested: 0.3, 600, and 900 ng/mL. The recovery rates were 99.64%, 95.31%, and 100.01%, respectively. Baricitinib had an overall average recovery of 97.65% and tolbutamide of 91.04%.

CONCLUSIONS

This LC-MS/MS-quantification method for assessing Baricitinib in biological fluids is unique, rapid, robust, sensitive, selective, rugged, and has excellent recovery. It has many advantages over prior methods.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors affirm that this research was carried out without any commercial or financial ties that could be interpreted as potential conflicts of interest.

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